

DIRECTIONS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF REFORMS AIMED AT FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE PUBLIC SAFETY SYSTEM AND INCREASING ITS EFFECTIVENESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8201791>

Abstract

Completely new mechanisms and procedures of holistic management and continuous control were introduced on the basis of the "republic – region – district – mahalla" system, ensuring peace and stability in the country through effective coordination of activities to ensure public security of internal affairs bodies and other state bodies.

The participation of subjects in ensuring public safety was also clearly defined, their main tasks and mutual interaction in this regard were fixed. The article highlights the results and prospects of reforms aimed at further improving and increasing the effectiveness of the public safety system.

Key words: national guard, internal affairs bodies, public order, public security, public order protection, public security, reforms, legal framework, organization, personnel training, digitalization, logistics.

Glorification of human dignity, ensuring the rights and freedoms, legal interests of everyone has become the priority direction of the reforms implemented in our country.

As the President noted, "Certainly, human value is not some abstract, lofty concept for us. By human dignity, we mean, first of all, the peaceful and safe life of every citizen, the provision of his fundamental rights and freedoms" [3].

Today we are building a new state of Uzbekistan, a free civil society, based on populist and democratic principles. For this purpose, we are giving priority to the strengthening of peace and stability, which is our priceless wealth, as the most important task" [2].

It is known that the peaceful and safe life of citizens, the provision of their fundamental rights and freedoms, and the effective organization of public security activities are directly related to many aspects. In the research conducted in this regard, "the provision of public safety is one of the stable, important and mandatory elements of the existence of the state" [20; 161- p], "the provision of public safety is considered the main activity of the state, in particular, its law enforcement bodies, in any era" [21; 91-p], "ensuring public safety is the most important issue of the agenda for the development of the law enforcement system of the state" [22; 167- p], we can agree with the given conclusions.

Over the past period, completely new mechanisms and procedures for organizing public safety work in our country based on the principle of "serving the interests of the people" have been introduced, and mutual purposeful cooperation between state bodies and public structures has been established.

In the implementation of reforms aimed at further improving the system of public safety and increasing its efficiency, it is necessary to "clearly define the prospective directions of the state policy in the field of public safety [5], to form an integrated system of public safety, to

establish effective activities from the lowest level of the system to the republican level, to introduce modern working methods. strengthening law and order and legality in our country, ensuring the peace and tranquility of the population [4], etc.

President Sh.M. Mirziyoev As part of the reforms carried out in this field at the initiative of, especially in the provision of public security, creating effective mechanisms for serving the population and cooperating with the general public, increasing the efficiency of the field services by providing them with new generation technologies and software systems, and organizing service activities based on appropriate models issues such as modeling became important.

Based on the essence of the reforms implemented in the field of public safety, we can consider their results by dividing them into the following directions.

Legal provision of public security activities. It is known that one of the main signs of effective organization of activity is the legal regulation of its purpose, tasks and functions. Norms - strengthen the legal status and functions of the subject and object of management, increase the responsibility of each participant of the management system of society [19; 14-p].

It can be seen from the analysis of the reforms implemented in the field of public safety in recent years that in this process, special attention is paid to the creation of the legal basis of the activity based on the requirements of the time.

In particular, the adoption of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies" of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at eliminating gaps, ambiguities and conflicts in the legal field that regulates today's extremely responsible, very diverse and diverse activities of internal affairs bodies, as well as regarding the activities of internal affairs bodies within the framework of a separate law. by providing a single systematization of the main rules, it started a new phase of reforms in the system [24; 71-p]

In improving the legal foundations of public safety, clearly demarcate the duties, functions and responsibilities of the entities that provide public safety and participate in it [7], exclude repetitive and obsolete powers, strengthen the level of material and technical support that ensures the promptness and efficiency of units, modern scientific and technical tools and information and communication technologies, including improving the quality of public services [17; 11-p].

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of public security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation" is primarily aimed at ensuring the peaceful life of the population within the framework of large-scale reforms in our country, as well as forming a culture of the rule of law and public security in society. The important aspect of this document is, the decree created a legal basis for the implementation of complex measures to ensure public safety. Until that time, there were no full-fledged legal bases in this regard. Based on this decree, the concept of public safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the strategy for the development of the public safety system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2025 were approved.

An important document defining the state policy in the field of public safety, which is considered one of the main areas of national security, is the "Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the main concepts related to public safety, national interests in the field of public safety, the main directions of public policy, the main principles of activity, by the state Important issues such as regulation, concept implementation mechanisms and expected results have been legally strengthened [5].

In this regard, it should be acknowledged that until now there were a number of misconceptions about the true meaning of the concept of public safety, and now its meaning, clear and fluent rule has been regulated on the basis of a legal document [16]. In particular, public security is a state of protection of society from illegal aggressions, social and ethnic conflicts, emergency situations and other threats, which serves the sustainable development of society and ensures the realization of human rights, freedoms and legitimate interests.

The purpose of the "Strategy for the development of the system of public safety in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2025", which plays an important role in the improvement of the legal basis of public safety, is to develop and effectively implement measures to introduce a qualitatively new system of public safety in the country, to develop the legal basis of the sector. is [25; 10-p].

At the same time, as a way to eliminate the serious consequences of road traffic accidents and the sharp increase in traffic violations, to strengthen the responsibility measures against those who regularly violate traffic safety rules and those who commit serious traffic accidents, including advanced foreign taking into account experiences, introducing a measure of criminal-legal impact in the form of long-term deprivation of the right to drive a vehicle, introduction of the procedure for recovery of material damages from the heads of organizations or bodies in charge of road or engineering-communication infrastructure objects that caused unsatisfactory condition of the road traffic accident, especially the death, as well as determining their responsibility, the behavior represented by the cases of "road hooliganism" committed by vehicle drivers - specific measures were also established regarding the introduction of administrative responsibility for actions, improvement of legal mechanisms for holding pedestrians accountable for violating traffic rules [26; 239-p].

Management and organization of public safety activities. Management of public safety activities is the execution and ordering activity of authorized state bodies and public organizations in this field [27; 2-p].

In order to ensure peace and stability in the country based on the "republic - region - district - neighborhood" system, the introduction of integrated management and continuous control mechanisms, the effective coordination of the activities of internal affairs and other state bodies to ensure public safety, within the framework of the ongoing reforms, the following completely new mechanisms put into practice [4]:

firstly, it was assumed that neighborhood law enforcement centers would be established step by step on the basis of the base points of the internal affairs bodies. According to it, the neighborhood law enforcement center is considered to be the main subordinate link of ensuring public safety in the area, preventing offenses and fighting crime, and on its basis, the relevant sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies, the coordinated activities of the National Guard and other state bodies, and the systematic organization of public safety and the task of coordination was assigned to the prevention inspector;

secondly, by improving the structure of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, in order to introduce a single system of management and coordination of the activities of the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies to maintain public order and security, the Department of Public Security was established and its main tasks were determined;

thirdly, in order to ensure the effective use of existing forces and means by optimizing the structures of activities of regional internal affairs bodies to maintain public order and ensure safety, as well as leadership positions, due to the elimination of some leadership positions, the

position of deputy head of regional and lower internal affairs bodies - head of the Public Security Service was introduced, and coordination of the activities of patrol-post, road patrol service units, as well as the implementation of targeted preventive measures in neighborhoods and public places, at the expense of previous convictions, probation working with the taken persons and organizing the night service were defined as his main tasks.

On this basis, the lower levels of the internal affairs bodies were strengthened in order to maintain public order in the neighborhoods, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent crimes and strengthen the fight against crime [14].

Within the framework of the reforms, significant work is being done to increase the tourism potential of the republic, in particular, comprehensive measures are being taken to create favorable conditions for tourists and to build the reputation of Uzbekistan as a safe country to visit [6].

As a result of reforms in the field of management and organization of security activities in transport and tourism facilities, a unique national system for ensuring safe tourism was formed. This system combines measures to maintain public order, early prevention of violations and fight against crime in tourism places and in railway and air transport infrastructure facilities that are actively used by tourists for movement across the republic. This served to move to a qualitatively new stage of effective provision of public safety in transport and tourism facilities [23; 68-p].

It can be seen from the analysis of the reforms being carried out in the field of improving the management and organization of public security activities that special attention is paid to the widespread introduction of digitization in this field.

It is known that digitization is a modern convenience that is entering all fields and industries today. Today, these facilities are fully implemented in the public safety system. In the future, in the field of ensuring public safety, it is decided to reduce paper-based work as much as possible and to increase the share of documents kept in electronic form to 90% [15].

In addition, as part of the implemented reforms, the concepts of "Safe capital", "Smooth and safe road", "Safe house", "Safe yard", "E-patrol" systems, "Smart neighborhood" [11], "E-public safety" proved that the use of new work methods in organizing activities based on information and "Safe City" hardware and software complexes creates many conveniences [28; 157-p].

Training of personnel for public safety activities. One of the most important measures to ensure public safety is to provide personnel who are aware of modern science and technology for the operation of this field based on specific mechanisms.

On the basis of the relevant decisions of the President, the reforms implemented in this direction are, firstly, the establishment of a system of training highly qualified specialists in the field of public security based on advanced international standards; secondly, based on the requirements of the times, to increase the personnel capacity of the units in this field [13]; thirdly, to ensure the growth of employees according to their qualifications [8]; fourthly, it covers further improvement of intellectual and professional capacity of leading personnel in effective management of forces and means [12].

Material and technical provision of public safety activities. There are a number of factors affecting the effectiveness of public safety activities, among which material and technical support takes an important place [18; 11- p]. To date, there is no field of human activity that has not undergone positive changes as a result of the introduction of modern technologies.

Currently, innovative technologies are rapidly developing and entering all aspects of our life, which imposes the task of introducing new innovative techniques and technologies to the activities of public safety, as well as other areas of society, and increasing competition tolerance using high technologies.

In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "introduced a number of changes in the field, first of all, it is required to improve the modern material and technical base of services in the street and public places, based on best practices abroad [1; 334-p] serves as a program. In particular, within the framework of the ongoing reforms, the introduction of employees' service with a personal video recorder (body camera), intelligent cameras with the possibility of monitoring and independent control ("Smart"), provision of electronic system tablets, special cars and motorcycles designed for patrolling and technology [10] for formalizing and reviewing criminal cases, saving the time of field workers, increasing the mobility of forces and means, ensuring the inevitability of punishment in a timely and prompt manner, it allows preventing corruption cases, quickly managing forces and means, and quickly reacting to citizens' appeals.

In today's era of globalization, new threats and dangers are emerging, methods and means of committing crimes, and goals are changing. In this sense, it can be said that in addition to the achieved achievements, there are important priorities that are planned to be implemented in the future in order to further increase the efficiency of public safety.

These priorities determine the prospects for improving the effectiveness of public safety activities.

In this regard, the "Strategy for the development of the public safety system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2025" and the principle of "For human dignity" developed on the basis of advanced foreign and national experiences in ensuring public safety and aimed at guaranteeing the protection of the population from any threats. documents such as "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026" are gaining importance in order to determine the priorities of reforms aimed at ensuring unconditional provision of human rights and interests.

In accordance with the 16th goal of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" (to ensure public safety, to create an effective system of timely identification and elimination of the conditions that led to the commission of crimes), the crime prevention system is qualitatively new bringing to a stage, fundamentally improving the activities of the patrol service for maintaining public order; In accordance with the 17th goal (Formation of a new image of law enforcement bodies and directing their activities to effectively protect the interests of the people, human dignity, rights and freedoms), turning the internal affairs bodies into a pro-people professional structure as a reliable defender of the people and directing them to target work with the population, as well as a number of measures are being implemented to turn the principle of "law is priority, punishment is inevitable" into the main criterion [6].

As a conclusion, it can be said that as a result of the reforms aimed at further improving the public security system and increasing its effectiveness, the protection of citizens' rights and freedoms, society and state interests from illegal attacks will be qualitatively higher. By orienting the service activities of employees in the provision of public security to help citizens, the trust of the population in the competent state bodies for the provision of public security is achieved.

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